

D5.7 — Report of “Workflows for omics data integration”

An ELIXIR Norway ELIXIR3 deliverable

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Context

This report describes work carried out for Deliverable 5.7, “Workflows for omics data integration”.

The aim of D5.7 is to support workflows that can process and integrate omics data in secure computing environments. Such workflows depend on reproducible access to software components, workflow engines, reference resources, and secure compute infrastructure.

The work reported here provides an initial workflow execution demonstrator inside TSD/Colossus. An existing ATAC-seq Snakemake workflow was imported into TSD, configured to use Galaxy CVMFS (CernVM-File System) BioContainers, and executed through Apptainer on the Colossus submit host. The demonstrator focused on the initial workflow stages, including setup and raw-data quality control.

This is not yet a complete multi-omics integration workflow. Rather, it establishes the practical execution pattern needed for future omics data integration work inside secure environments.

Background

Omics data integration workflows often combine multiple computational steps, including raw-data quality control, trimming, mapping, feature or peak generation, count generation, annotation, and downstream statistical analysis. These workflows require consistent access to software versions and reference resources.

In secure compute environments, these requirements are difficult to meet because direct internet access and uncontrolled software installation are restricted. This makes it important to establish a reproducible model for workflow execution where sensitive input data remain inside the Trusted Research Environment, while non-sensitive software components are provided through controlled infrastructure.

The D5.7 proof-of-concept builds on the D5.5 framework and the D5.6 implementation work by testing a practical workflow execution pattern for omics data processing inside TSD/Colossus.

Current challenges

Several challenges must be addressed before omics workflows can be routinely executed and integrated inside secure environments:

- workflow source code must be imported through approved channels;
- software dependencies must be available without direct internet access;
- containerized tools must be executable in the secure HPC environment;
- workflow configuration must refer to resources available inside the project area;
- reference data and indexes must be available in controlled locations;
- workflow engines and schedulers may behave differently from open environments;
- pipelines may assume Singularity while the infrastructure provides Apptainer;
- reproducibility material must avoid including sensitive data.

The demonstrator addressed these issues using synthetic input data and CVMFS-hosted BioContainers.

Delivery

Selection of demonstrator workflow

An existing ATAC-seq Snakemake workflow developed by Martina Visnovska¹ was selected as the demonstrator workflow.

ATAC-seq was a suitable first test because it represents a common omics workflow pattern, including raw-read quality control, preprocessing, mapping, signal generation, and downstream analysis. The current demonstrator focused on the first stages of this workflow, while preserving the possibility of extending the test to later stages.

Secure-environment workflow import

The workflow source code was imported into TSD through the approved TSD portal mechanism. Since the TSD environment does not provide direct internet access, the workflow was cloned outside TSD, packaged as a tarball, imported through the portal, and unpacked inside the TSD project area.

¹ <https://gitlab.com/epigen/mnaseqfastqtoreadcounts>
<https://gitlab.com/epigen/atacseqfastqtoreadcounts>

The work was carried out in the TSD project [p3066](#), with workflow execution on the Colossus submit host:

p3066-hpc-01

The workflow was placed under:

/tsd/p3066/cluster/home/p3066-pavelva/cvmfs-poc/atacseqfastqtoreadcounts

Software components from Galaxy CVMFS

The demonstrator used the Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers repository as the software source:

/cvmfs/singularity.galaxyproject.org/all

The following containers required by the workflow were confirmed to be available:

fastqc:0.11.9--hdfd78af_1
multiqc:1.10.1--py_0
trimmomatic:0.39--1
bowtie2:2.4.5--py39hd2f7db1_2
samtools:1.6--hb116620_7
deeptools:3.5.0--py_0
picard:2.23.3--0
macs2:2.2.7.1--py39hbf8eff0_5
bedtools:2.30.0--hc088bd4_0
ucsc-bedgraphtobigwig:377--h446ed27_1

This confirmed that the required software components for several stages of the ATAC-seq workflow can be resolved from CVMFS inside the secure environment.

Workflow execution environment

The workflow was executed using:

Snakemake 8.27.0
Apptainer 1.5.0-1.e19

The original workflow scripts use [singularity exec](#). Since Apptainer is the available runtime, a local compatibility wrapper was used to redirect [singularity](#) calls to Apptainer. This allowed the existing workflow scripts to run without being rewritten.

The final Snakemake execution used the greedy scheduler because the default ILP scheduler encountered a PuLP/CBC solver issue in the environment.

Lightweight test data

The demonstrator used tiny paired-end synthetic FASTQ files and a minimal placeholder reference FASTA. This was intentional: the goal was to test secure workflow execution and use of CVMFS-hosted BioContainers, not to validate biological results.

The synthetic data allowed the workflow to be executed without moving real sensitive data or large reference datasets during the initial test.

Successful workflow stages

The following workflow stages were successfully executed:

```
init
raw_data_qc
fastqc_raw
multiqc_raw
```

The `init` stage generated expected setup and presence-check outputs, including:

```
00_init.done
00_params.done
00_presence/00_presence.done
00_presence/01_files/sampleA_R1.present
00_presence/01_files/sampleA_R2.present
00_presence/02_sample_lanes/sampleA_L001.present
00_presence/03_samples/sampleA.present
params.sh
```

The `raw_data_qc` stage successfully executed FastQC and MultiQC using CVMFS-hosted containers.

Generated FastQC outputs included:

```
01_raw_data_qc/fastqc_sampleA_R1.done
01_raw_data_qc/fastqc_sampleA_R2.done
01_raw_data_qc/fastqc/sampleA_R1_fastqc.zip
01_raw_data_qc/fastqc/sampleA_R1_fastqc.html
01_raw_data_qc/fastqc/sampleA_R2_fastqc.zip
01_raw_data_qc/fastqc/sampleA_R2_fastqc.html
```

Generated MultiQC outputs included:

```
01_raw_data_qc/multiqc.done
01_raw_data_qc/multiqc/multiqc_report.html
01_raw_data_qc/multiqc/multiqc_data/multiqc_data.json
```

01_raw_data_qc/multiqc/multiqc_data/multiqc_general_stats.txt
01_raw_data_qc/multiqc/multiqc_data/multiqc_fastqc.txt
01_raw_data_qc/multiqc/multiqc_data/multiqc_sources.txt

The MultiQC log confirmed:

```
multiqc : This is MultiQC v1.10.1  
fastqc  : Found 2 reports  
multiqc : MultiQC complete
```

Reproducibility material

A separate reproducibility package was prepared for an ELIXIR Oslo repository². This package contains the practical instructions and scripts used to recreate the demonstrator, including:

```
patch_cvmfs_poc_config.py  
run_cvmfs_poc.sh  
CVMFS_TSD_POC_PATCHLOG.md  
reproducibility-report.md
```

The reproducibility material is intended to document the exact technical steps without overloading the deliverable report itself.

Outcomes

1. Initial omics workflow demonstrator completed

An existing ATAC-seq workflow was successfully used as a demonstrator for omics workflow execution inside TSD/Colossus.

The demonstrator confirms that workflow source code, secure project storage, the Colossus submit host, Snakemake, Apptainer, and Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers can be combined into a working execution model.

2. Raw omics quality-control workflow steps executed

The first omics workflow stage tested was raw-data quality control. FastQC and MultiQC were successfully executed through the workflow using CVMFS-hosted containers.

This is an important early stage in many omics workflows and provides a practical basis for extending the test to later workflow stages.

² <https://github.com/elixir-oslo/tsd-cvmfs-workflow-poc>

3. Secure execution pattern established

The work established a reusable pattern for omics workflow execution in secure environments:

1. import workflow source code through approved mechanisms;
2. keep input data inside the TSD project area;
3. use the Colossus submit host for workflow execution;
4. use Snakemake for orchestration;
5. resolve software containers from Galaxy CVMFS;
6. execute containers through Apptainer;
7. keep reproducibility material separate from sensitive data.

4. Basis for future omics data integration work

Although the current demonstrator does not yet perform complete multi-omics integration, it establishes the necessary execution foundation. Later stages can build on this by adding realistic ATAC-seq data, reference genomes, mapping, peak calling, count generation, and downstream integration with other omics data types.

Conclusion

D5.7 has delivered an initial secure-environment workflow execution demonstrator for omics data processing.

An existing ATAC-seq Snakemake workflow was imported into TSD, connected to Galaxy CVMFS BioContainers, and executed on the Colossus submit host through Apptainer. The successful execution of `init` and `raw_data_qc`, including FastQC and MultiQC, demonstrates that omics workflow components can run inside the secure environment while using non-sensitive software components from CVMFS.

This work provides the foundation for extending the demonstrator to full ATAC-seq processing and later to broader omics data integration workflows.